

Language Resources in Estonian Sign Language Research

Péter Zalán ROMANEK and Christian RATHMANN
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EVKUR

Eesti viipekeele uurimisrühm

HARIDUS- JA
TEADUSMINISTEERIUM

projekti toetab

Contextualization

Research questions

Design

Key Insights and Challenges

Discussion

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Contemporary Issues in Language Resources

Language Documentation (Fenlon et al, 2015; Quadros et al., 2022)

Lexical databases (Crasborn et al. 2016; Hochesang et al. 2018)

Annotation and lemmatization (Johnston, 2008; Johnston 2009; Schembri & Crasborn, 2010; Cormier et al. 2016; Fenlon & Hochgesang 2022)

Language resources, datasets, corpora (Johnston, 2008; Crasborn and de Meijer, 2012)

Data governance, management, archiving, access (Johnston, 2010; Reiner et al., 2024; Kuder, 2022)

AI-Generated Sign Languages (Desai et al. 2024, Rathmann & Romanek, 2025)

Contextualization: Estonia

Estonian Sign Language (EVK) - an under-documented language

Recognized as indigenous language under the Language Act of (2007)

Estonian Language Strategy 2021-2032: focus on digital state and resource development

Establishment of Estonian Sign Language Research Lab (2024-)

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(1) Which toolkits and procedures can be developed to host language resources in Estonian Sign Language?

(2) How can the sustainable development of language resources can for Estonian Sign Language be ensured?

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Signbank EVK Lexical Documentation

Points of Departure

Signbank 2.0 for Sign Languages (Quadros et al. 2024)

Visuolab (Rathmann et al. 2024)

- **Global Signbank** Cassidy et al., 2018; Crasborn et al., 2012, 2018)
- **ID Glosses** (Quadros, 2016; Quadros et al., 2020)
- **Search system** (Scolari, 2022)
- SignBank 2.0.
 - **Search functions** including handshapes, number of hands, handedness and location
 - **Standard glosses** (for annotation)

Signbank 2.0 for Estonian Sign Language

EVK Lexical Database

 EVKUR

☰ < ET ▾

Kodu

▶ 0:00 / 0:18

⚠ ID: 586 REDIGEERI

! Platvormi kohta

🔍 Otsi viipekirjeid

📧 Kontakt

📖 Korduma kippuvad küsimused

▶ 0:00

⚠ ID: 589 REDIGEERI

Tere tulemast eesti viipekeelele SignBank Estonia 2.0 platvormile

 TALLINNA ÜLIKOOL

 HUMBOLDT-UNIVERSITÄT ZU BERLIN

 EVKUR
Eesti viipekeele uurimiskeskus

 HARIDUS- JA TEADUSMINISTEERIUM
projektid teetab

(1) Users' Autonomy I

Kasutajad 🖐️

Trükkige otsingusõna 🔍

ID: 514

List de usuários da plataforma

Tela de Usuários

Nesta tela estão listados todos os usuários do sistema, com os dados:

Data de cadastro do usuário; Nome do usuário; Se o usuário é surdo ou ouvinte; E-mail do usuário; 1ª língua do usuário

Além dos status de aprovador, se ele está ativado ou desativado e o seu tipo de perfil (administrador ou postador).

Nesta tela também é possível realizar pesquisa de texto ou alterar o

REDIGEERI

kuvatakse 4 / 4 kasutajat

JÄRJESTUS: VALI ▼

LOOMISE KUUPÄEV	NIMI/IDENTITEET	MEILIAADDRESS	ESIMENE KEEL	KINNITAJA	STAATUS	PROFI
2020/07/16	Administrador Ger... Kuulja	admin@admin.com	Keel on kustutatud	jah	aktiveeritud	Adn
2025/06/16	Péter Zalán Romanek...	peter.romanek@tlu...	eesti	jah	aktiveeritud	Adn

(i) Management tools

(ii) Multilingual access

(iii) Interactive dashboard

(1) Users' Autonomy II

Tähendusväli

kuvatakse 10 / 91 tähendusvälja

Trükkige otsingu...

JÄRJESTUS: VALI

LOOMISE KUUPÄEV	VÄRV	NIMETUS		
2022/11/09	● #0A0A0A9F	toiduained	↻	🗑️
2022/11/09	● #863535FF	loomad	↻	🗑️
2022/11/09	● #CCB918F0	ühendused/sihtasutused	↻	🗑️
2022/11/09	● #0B0EA8F5	joogid	↻	🗑️
2022/11/09	● #CCCCCCFF	omadused	↻	🗑️
2022/11/09	● #CCCCCCFF	linnad/linnaosad/maakonnad	↻	🗑️
2022/11/09	● #1497CCCF	värvid	↻	🗑️
2022/11/09	● #1C23CCFF	nädalapäevad	↻	🗑️

Dashboard:
(i.) accessible
and
(ii.) editable
interface

(2) Sign entries

with lexical, phonological, morphological, syntactic and semantical information

H

4 viipekirjet

HÄBI-2 HÄBI-1 HÄBELIK

HÕORDUMINE

HÄBI-1

VIIPE PILT VIIPE VIDEO

PÕHILISED OMADUSED

LEMMA: HÄBI-1
INGLISKEELNE LEMMA: SHAME-1
GLOSS-ID: HÄBI-1
INGLISKEELNE GLOSS-ID: SHAME-1
VIIPE TÕLGE (EESTI) : shame
VIIPE TÕLGE (INGLISE KEELES): shame

IKOONILISUS

SÜNTAKS

POSTITUSED JA MÄRKUSED

TÄIENDAVAD OMADUSED

KAS SEE ON SÕNARAAMATUS? Jah
STAATUS: Avaldatud

0 ESINEMISKORDA:

Otsi:

Tunnus Keel

🔗 🗨️ 📘 🐦

(3) Machine-readability: Integration of Gloss-IDs

CREATION DATE	VIDEO	GLOSS ID	TIME	LANGUAGE
2024/04/19	FLN_GR_F17_entrevista_cam03 translation not given (Florianópolis - Santa Catarina) Ronice Müller de Quadros	THANKS	00:00:07 - 00:00:07	en
116 OCCURRENCES:				
Search for:				
		Identifier	Language	
Displaying 10 of 116 occurrences				
2024/04/19	FLN_GR_F17_entrevista_cam03 translation not given (Florianópolis - Santa Catarina) Ronice Müller de Quadros	FLN_GR_F02_entrevista_cam03 Author: Ana Regina e Souza Campello Responsible researcher: Ronice Müller de Quadros; Place: Florianópolis - Santa Catarina - Brasil Start: 00:05:08 End: 00:05:08 ACEITAR Language: pt Identifier: Tier_key - 1		
2024/04/19	FLN_GR_F17_entrevista_cam03 translation not given (Florianópolis - Santa Catarina) Ronice Müller de Quadros	FLN_GR_F02_entrevista_cam03 Author: Ana Regina e Souza Campello Responsible researcher: Ronice Müller de Quadros; Place: Florianópolis - Santa Catarina - Brasil Start: 00:19:56 End: 00:19:56 ACEITAR Language: pt Identifier: Tier_key - 1		
2024/04/19	FLN_GR_F17_entrevista_cam03 translation not given (Florianópolis - Santa Catarina) Ronice Müller de Quadros	SIGN-patricia	00:00:24 - 00:00:25	en

(4) Robust search engine I

! Platvormi kohta

🔍 Otsi viipekirjeid

- Käekuju
- Sõnad
- Kategooriad
- Võrgustik
- Vaata kõiki

📧 Kontakt

🗉 Korduma kippuvad küsimused

[Kodu](#) / [Käekuju](#) / [Vaata kõiki](#)

Valige otsingutüüp

ÜLDINE OTSING OTSING SÕNA ALGUSE JÄRGI TÄPSE VASTE OTSING

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V X Y Z

User Manuals for lexical documentation

Comprehensive user manuals for lexical documentation

Kasutusjuhend Märkendamine eesti viipekeeles (mustand)

Péter Zalán Romanek, Tallinna Ülikool
Christian Rathmann, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin / Tallinna Ülikool,
Jäni Pärigma, Tallinna Ülikool

Kasutusjuhend Signbank 2.0 eesti viipekeecele (mustand)

Triin Jõeveer, Tallinna Ülikool
Péter Zalán Romanek, Tallinna Ülikool
Christian Rathmann, Tallinna Ülikool

4.1.6. Koht

There are two fields to be filled out, the main area and the specific location, if a sign has a change of location fill out the information related to the beginning of the sign, and in the notes (stage 3) you can write what that change is. The locations available are:

4.1.6.1. Pea ja kael

kukal	alahuul	põsk
põsesarn	lõug	kõrv
silm	nägu	otsmik
pea (ülemine või külg)	lõualuu	suu
kael	nina	huulte kohal
meelekoht	keel	lõua all

4.1.6.2. Kehatüvi

kaelaalune	selg	riid
------------	------	------

2.1. Mudeli põhistruktuuri ülesehitus

1-Lemma
1-Gloss-ID
1-Gloss-ID inglise keeles
1-Sign_RH
1-Sign_LH
1-tõlge
1-Commentar_annotator
1-Commentar_translator

1-Lemma
[0]
1-Gloss-ID
[0]
1-Gloss-ID English
[0]
1-Sign_RH
[0]
1-Sign_LH
[0]
1-Translation
[0]

Visuolab EVK Digital Repository

Visuolab

EVK Digital Repository

(a) Sign Language Portal

(b) Creation and publication of sign language materials

(c) Interactive classroom teaching and learning

(d) Sign-language Assessment

(e) Operation with SignBank 2.0.

The screenshot displays the Visuolab website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with a 'Menüü' button, the 'Visuolab' logo, a language selector set to 'ET', and a user profile for 'Tere, Πετρούλι'. The main content area features a header for 'Eesti viipekeelee portal' with a search bar and a dropdown menu. Below this, there is a section titled 'Uued ressursid' (New resources) with a 'Vaata rohkem' button. The page includes a sidebar with a menu of resources such as 'EVK portal', 'Raamatukogu ressursid', 'Eesti viipekeel', 'Uurimisprojektid', 'Kursused', and 'Minu ressursid'. A video player is visible in the sidebar, showing a man speaking. The main content area also includes a search bar with the text 'Sisesta mis tahes märksõna' and a dropdown menu with 'Kõik kategoor...'. A 'Muuda bännerit' button is present below the search bar.

Sign Language Portal

- EVK portal
- Raamatukogu ressursid
- Eesti viipekeel
- Uurimisprojektid
- Kursused
- [+ Lisa uus ressurss](#)
- Minu ressursid
- Multifunktsionaalne tuba
- Meist
- Tugi

Multifunktsionaalne tuba

Uuri lähemalt

Minu ressursid

Uuri lähemalt

Mis toimub...

42 Registreeritud inimesed	57 Ressursid	3 Allalaadimised
--------------------------------------	------------------------	----------------------------

Uued ressursid

[Vaata rohkem](#)

Eesti viipekeele põhigrammatika kirjeldus

Graduate Program in Brazilian Sign Language Translation and Interpretation

Glossary in Brazilian Sign Language: Regional Signs from Gurupi

2. Sign Language Publications

 Raamatukogu ressurss • Akadeemiline

Eesti viipekeele põhigrammatika kirjeldus

Tallinna Ülikool

Jari Pärigma • Peter Zalan Romanek

 V-book

 Hariduse valdkond: Keeled ja kunstid

 Ressursi tüüp: V-raamat

 Haridustase: Kõrgharidus

 Keel: inglise keel • rahvusvaheline viipekeel

 Avaldatud: 2025/11/27

 Place: Estonia

 Vaata sisu

 Salvesta

 Jaga

 Muuda

Creation and publication of

- (a) video books,
- (b) teaching, learning and assessment materials,
- (c) signed papers / videos for language documentary and learning / teaching activities

3. Multifunctional Rooms

Activity type

Select:

- Comments only:** participants can only comment (with text and videos).
- Submission:** participants can comment (with text and videos) and record or upload videos to be evaluated.
- Simultaneous:** participants watch a media (video or pdf) and record a response video that rolls at same time.
- Video meeting:** participants join a real-time video call.
- Consecutive:** Interpreter listens to speaker/see image, takes notes, and then translates what was said/written

Cancel Continue

4. Sign Language Assessment Tools

Menu VisuoLab EN Hello, Sarah

Video Classroom > Spaces > Translation Stud... > First Assignment...

Reception

Multiple Choice
It presents a question or statement followed by several options, where you can choose the correct answer from the provided choices.

Edit banner ID: 555

First Assignment: Fun poll: How important is memorising information? Time Left: 00:10:00

QUESTION 1
This is counting as: 1.00 Report

What is the key sign on this video?

Finish Activity Stop Activity

← Previous Next →
Set of questions

Finish Activity

A

B

C

D

Finish Activity

Spaces Activities Pads Resources Grades Scales

Create Custom Scales
Use this page to create custom scales for your activities. Once created, all spaces can access and use these scales for consistent evaluations.

ID: page-create-custom-scales Edit banner

SCALE TITLE

Default
0% - 100%

Competent
Not competent, Competent

Likert Scale - Productive
Not at all productive, Not very productive, Average, Productive, Very productive

Competent
Not Competent, Competent

Self-evaluation (comprehension)
complete, almost completely, mostly completely, partially complete, not complete (more than half understood), incomplete (more than half understood)

Fluency
not fluid, less fluid, not so fluid, fluid, good fluid, very fluid

Activity type

ID: form-new-activity-activity-type-stepper-2 Edit banner

Select Activity Type:

Freeform Activities Assessment Activities

Reception: Create a quiz or test participants understanding of the subject

Multiple Choice **True/False**

Matrix **Drag&Drop**

Short Answer **H5P Activities**

Production: participants produce and submit videos about the subject

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Key Insights

- **Contextuality:** embeddedness in the Estonian context
- **Sustainability:** institutional and stakeholder collaboration
- **Accessibility:** open to everyone (WCAG-compliant)
- **User-friendliness:** designed for the Deaf community, Deaf professionals, and researchers
- **Reproducibility:** ensures replicable EVK research
- **Data governance:** GDPR-, FAIR-, and CARE-aligned
- **Retrievability:** consistent metadata system

Contextualization

Research questions

Solutions

Key Insights

Discussion

Discussion: Access and Application

- Language documentation and archiving
- Lexical documentation of EVK
- Sign-language teaching, learning, and assessment
- Sign-language interpreting and translation
- Corpus design

Broader Implications

- Digital resource development for EVK (Schembri, 2010; Kopf et al., 2022)
- Foundation for language-related service design (Efthimiou et al., 2019)
- Basis for AI-generated sign languages (Desai, 2024; Rathmann & Romanek, 2025)

Thank you!